

M12: Third annual feedback to other work packages about final climate information sources

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01**1. Introduction****02****2. Communication with other WPs (task 3.1)****03****3. Downscaling (task 3.2)****04****4. Temporal combination (task 3.3)**

Milestones and Deliverables so far

No	Description	Leader	Date
1	M8, provision of early guidance on initial selection of data as input to WP4,	UOXF	30/04/2023
2	M9, first annual feedback to other work packages about new climate information sources	SMHI	31/12/2023
3	M10, second annual feedback to other work packages about new climate information sources	SMHI	31/12/2024
4	D3.1, provision of first combined information,	BSC	31/12/2024

WP3 Introduction

- This deliverable report (M12) represents an up-to-date status for Dec 2025

WP3 Introduction

Objectives:

- Deliver actionable, high-resolution climate data to support adaptation efforts.
- Spatial climate **downscaling** (Task 3.2) and **time combination** (Task 3.3) methodologies and products.
- Ensure outputs are demand-driven through collaboration with decision-makers and ASPECT use cases (Task 3.1).

Climate Downscaling:

- Transforms global climate model outputs into high-resolution, regionally relevant data, determined by co-development
- Addresses global model limitations in representing local/regional climate features.
- Enhances spatial resolution and physical accuracy for specific geographic regions.

Time Combination:

- Integrates climate information seamlessly across various time scales.
- Co-developed by climate scientists and users to meet real-world needs.
- User interactions identified key objectives for combination methods during the reporting period.

Communication with other WPs

- WP3 partners attend WP4+5 regular meetings and case study meetings to define roles and contributions in the process of user interaction in individual super-user cases (see right panel), including technical details (variables, regions, visualization, data formats).

Statistical downscaling of seasonal and multi-annual predictions and statistical downscaling of seasonal predictions of spring frosts with a focus on synoptic setting and trends.

Temporal merging of seasonal and multi-annual predictions and decadal predictions and climate projections. **(BSC leads, UOXF, CMCC)**

Statistical downscaling of precipitation in decadal predictions over UK/France/Spain.

Temporal merging of decadal predictions and climate projections (winter NAO - stormy conditions). **(MO leads, CMCC, BSC), UZag)**

Dynamical downscaling of extreme events (co-defined according to user needs) for a time frame 30 years ahead. **(CMCC leads, SMHI, UZAG)**

Statistical downscaling of temperature in decadal predictions over UK/France/Spain.

Temporal merging of decadal predictions and climate projections (summer NAO - heatwaves) and seasonal and multi-annual predictions (hot weather). **(MO leads, UOX, CMCC, BSC, MPI)**

Early-stage co-design with Save the Children as Super User. **(BSC leads)**

Downscaling

Types of Downscaling

- **Dynamical Downscaling:** Uses physics-based models
- **Statistical Downscaling:** Employs statistical methods including analog methods
- **Hybrid-statistical downscaling:** Combined statistical methods with GCM climate prediction for enhanced prediction skill

Downscaling

- Essential for assessing climate change impacts at local/regional levels.
- Provides detailed insights into changes in temperature, precipitation, and other variables.
- Supports adaptation and mitigation in key sectors: Agriculture, Water resources, Infrastructure planning

Progress

- **Year 1:** Explored different downscaling methods (WP3 Task 2), selected approaches, initiated development, and conducted first tests.
- **Year 2:** Refined methods and advanced development in response to stakeholder interaction. Testing for selected use cases.
- **Year 3 and 4 (ongoing):** Finalizing methods, data production, data publication and stakeholder communication

Statistical downscaling

Establishes **statistical relationships** between coarse-scale predictors and finer-scale.

Effectiveness influenced by:

- Temporal scale of data
- Metrics and decision functions
- Variables downscaled, predictors, and predictands

Efficient for resource-limited applications where dynamical downscaling is impractical

Approaches in ASPECT:

- **Interpolation** with Bias Adjustment/Regression Techniques (BSC)
- **Analogue-Based Methods:** Focus on atmospheric circulation/weather regimes (CMCC, BSC).
- **Hybrid Statistical Downscaling:** Combines statistical methods with prediction data (CMCC).

Statistical downscaling CMCC

Statistical downscaling with hybrid methods

Hybrid methods of statistical downscaling consist of two steps:

- in the first step, we use observational data to learn the statistical relationship between a target variable important to the user (often capturing some aspects of a climate risk) and a candidate driver (often describing the large-scale atmospheric circulation). This is the statistical part of the method.
- In the second step, we use the dynamical prediction systems to predict the large-scale driver (this is the dynamical step).
- Then, we feed this information into the statistical model we previously learned to obtain predictions of the target variables.

For further reading see e.g. [Maraun et al. 2010](#), [Ramon et al. 2021](#).

Observed target

Observed driver

Statistical model

Predicted driver

Predicted target

Statistical downscaling CMCC

Contribution to the Agricultural case study

In this case, the target variable is March frost occurrence in Catalonia, the large-scale atmospheric circulation drivers are blocking events, and the forecast horizon is seasonal (here, one month ahead).

Key points:

- A robust statistical link is established between the occurrence of atmospheric blocking events in the Euro-Atlantic domain and frost in Catalonia (right).
 - Hybrid predictions outperform climatology and multi-model ensemble of raw dynamical predictions.
- Also, they improve on best raw dynamical prediction system over specific areas (not shown).

Left: composites of anomalous monthly blocking frequency (colors) against March frost occurrence in Raimat. Dots mark grid points where the blocking composites are statistically significant at the 90 % significance level. Right: predictive power associated with the blocking composites: number of frost events (cyan bars) and frost likelihood (magenta lines) per correlation bin. The dashed black line represents the climatological probability of March frost occurrence. Blocking events are differentiated by type: ridge (top), omega (middle), and Rex (bottom).

Statistical downscaling CMCC

Winter precipitation the Governance case study

In this case, the target variable is winter precipitation over the **Emilia-Romagna region**, the large-scale atmospheric circulation drivers are Euro-Atlantic Teleconnection Patterns such as the **North Atlantic Oscillation** and the Eastern-Atlantic Pattern, and the forecast horizon is decadal (here, up to ten years ahead). Key points:

- Complete assessment of method & skill underway.
- Established a robust statistical connection between Euro-Atlantic teleconnection indices and precipitation with multivariate linear regression models (not shown).
- Hybrid predictions wield good levels of skill according to preliminary skill evaluation (right).
- Next steps: assess skill for extreme precipitation events and summertime heat extremes.

Pearson correlation coefficient between observed and predicted winter (DJF) total accumulated precipitation averaged over forecast years 1-10. Dots mark grid points where the correlation is statistically significant at the 95% confidence level according to a one-tailed t-test accounting for time-series autocorrelations.

Statistical downscaling

BSC

Predictand	Large scale predictors
Temperature (min, max)	temperature at 850 hPa pressure level
	geopotential height at 850 hPa pressure level
	mean sea level pressure
Precipitation	zonal wind at 300 hPa
	zonal wind at 500 hPa
	zonal wind at 850 hPa
	geopotential height at 500 hPa pressure level
	geopotential height at 850 hPa pressure level
	relative humidity at 500 hPa pressure level
	relative humidity at 850 hPa pressure level
	mean sea level pressure

Statistical downscaling of seasonal climate indicators (BSC)

- Maps show June SPEI3 in 2003 (a known spring drought year) from raw (GCM) and downscaled forecasts at lead time 1 (i.e., model start month is May) and from observations
- Time series plots show the seasonal time series for the vineyard sites for the full study period; dashed lines indicate the ensemble max–min range (i.e., the uncertainty range).
- Maps demonstrate that downscaling captures the spatial patterns more realistically. When we analyse standard skill metrics (BSS10, BSS90, RPSS, correlation), we do not find significant differences between GCM and downscaled SPEI, so the key benefit is that downscaling preserves skill while adding valuable high-resolution spatial detail.
- Both products show reduced variance and overly smooth extremes; a simple variance inflation or bias-correction of downscaled SPEI could improve variability.
- Both vineyard sites show similar downscaling performance and smoothing behaviour, with no clear location-dependent differences.

Ralf: I guess a GCM prediction ensemble is meant here. Just curious how many ensemble members have been used in this analysis?

Statistical downscaling of decadal predictions (BSC)

Variables	Anomalies of mean air surface temperature (TAS) and precipitation (PR)
Prediction system	Multi-model ensemble of 13 systems from DCPA-hindcast
Lead time	Forecast years 1-5
Hindcast period	Start dates 1960 - 2013; Years 1961-2018
Region	Western Europe (34.5 °N to 58.8 °N; and 12 °W to 10 °E)
Reference data	ERA5land (0.1° x 0.1°)
Temporal resolution	Yearly/Daily

Methods

- Interpolations + 6 calibrations:
 - Bias adjustment
 - Mean Square Error minimization
 - Continuous Ranked Probability Skill minimization
 - Ratio Predictable Component based
 - Quantile Mapping
- Linear regressions:
 - Basic
 - 9 nearest neighbours
 - Using teleconnection index (obs or multimodel)
- Analogs with different predictors:
 - The own variable
 - Sea Level Pressure
 - Geopotential height at 500 hPa

Statistical downscaling of decadal predictions (BSC)

Some downscaling methods can increase predictability in certain regions compared to the original model output. For example, the analog method using PSL can generate predictive skill in locations where the interpolated data originally showed none.

The large spatial extent of the region allows the results obtained here to be applied to different case studies:

- Agricultural case study in Catalonia, Spain
- Pensions sector in the UK
- Disaster response in the UK

Comparative Analysis of Statistical Downscaling Methods in a Multimodel Framework for Decadal Climate Predictions over Western Europe. Moreno-Montes et al. (2025, under review, Climate Services)

Bicubic interpolation (21.4%)

Analogs (21.6%)

Anomaly Correlation Coefficient between the multi-model precipitation applying two downscaling methods and the ERA5 reanalysis. Hatched areas indicate regions where the correlation is not statistically significant.

Event-based dynamical downscaling (EBD) SMHI, Uni Zagreb

Objectives

- Develop EBD and utilize a process chain

Key achievements

- The concept of EBD
 - Detection of extreme events in ESM projections or predictions
 - Inexpensive model spinup
 - Dynamic downscaling of short event periods by a CPM in 3 km resolution
 - Automatic runtime processing of multiple (hundreds) events
 - Robustness assessment

Testing in Swedish domain for heat wave 2018

- publication Wang et al. (2025)
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.uclim.2025.102286>

Event-based dynamical downscaling (EBD) in Emilia-Romagna. SMHI, Uni Zagreb

Objectives

- Evaluate EBD method and adjust to Emilia-Romagna region

Key achievements

- After stakeholder consultations and scientific-technical testing: EBD reproduces observed events well; can be applied for climate projection/prediction heat waves and extreme precipitation events
- with large 12 km domain and local 3 km domain
- A method evaluation report will be part of a forthcoming formal deliverable by mid 2026

Event-based dynamical downscaling of extreme precipitation in Emilia-Romagna. SMHI, Uni Zagreb

70 extreme precipitation from recent climate as represented in ERA5 have been downscaled using the EBD method

Results demonstrate the added value of high-resolution downscaling, with the following findings:

- Resolution Impact: The HCLIM-3km better characterizes the regional rainfall maxima compared to the coarser-resolution datasets (ERA5 and HCLIM12). This highlights the necessity of higher resolution for representing local extreme during the events.
- Comparison to Observation (ERG5): HCLIM-3km shows a similar mean value for the regional maximum rain rate as the ERG5 local observations. However, it still appears slightly weaker in terms of capturing the highest regional extremes.
- Results for events representative for 2030 +/- 1 year, taken from a GCM projection ensemble (EC-Earth, 50 members) have been downscaled for recent climate and will be part of the user information by mid 2026.

Detection algorithms are described in a parallel milestone (M11) report by University of Zagreb

Spatial daily maximum of top 70 events of ERG5 in 1991-2023

Maximum daily rainfall among all grid points across the entire ER region during each individual event. The data is derived from 4 datasets (ERA5 25 km, HCLIM downscaling 12 km, HCLIM downscaling 3 km, ERG local observations 5 km)

Event-based dynamical downscaling: heat waves. SMHI, Uni Zagreb

Preliminary Results

- Testing downscaling of heat waves, it was found that an irrigation proxy is needed.
- Including an irrigation proxy, heat waves can be simulated reasonably well
- Heat waves in regionally downscaled events show a realistic urban heat island effect

Next:

- mass production (tens) of heat wave events and statistical evaluation

What kind of temperature ?

Event-based dynamical downscaling

SMHI, Uni Zagreb

Next steps

- Analysis of extreme precipitation events representative for 2030 +/- 1 year, taken from a GCM projection ensemble (EC-Earth, 50 members); will be part of the user information by mid 2026
- Mass production (tens) of heat wave events and statistical evaluation
- Understanding the physical conditions for recent and future climate extremes for the Emilia-Romagna region
- Assess the changing character of extreme events (frequency, intensity, duration)
- Likely: Exploring sensitivity to detection algorithms
- Long term: emulator of CPM and extremes

Summary of WP3 downscaling activities

A number of downscaling methodologies have been made available for climate prediction and projection. Applications so far are focusing on the Agricultural and Governance uses cases, as well as on testing domains in Sweden

- different variants of statistical downscaling, such as regression, analogues and hybrid methods have been applied to spring frost and water availability
- event-based dynamical downscaling of heat waves and extreme precipitation events for the Emilia-Romagna region as an ASPECT use case
- Advantages and limitations of the different methods have been explored and will be part of forthcoming user information via WP4

Options for up-scaling of methodologies will be discussed at the ASPECT GA in Feb 2025

Temporal Combining

“Stitching”

- uses best predictions as long as possible and replaces information with longer predictions/projections.

“Shadowing or Constraining or Subsampling”:

- picks (constrains) specific trajectories from projection ensembles that are close to, or “in the shadow” of a certain “target trajectory”.

“Merging”:

- Blends specific trajectories from different forecasts (e.g., from different forecast start dates) for the same forecast target into a joint forecast

“stitching”

“shadowing”

“merging”

Temporal Combining

Objectives

- To create and evaluate **seamless climate information** across time scales, using **temporal merging techniques** and apply them to **user-relevant adaptation** decisions.
 - To show users of long-term climate projections the added value of initialisation on the near time scale; motivate by illustrating with large scale drivers in storylines
- For shadowing: develop approaches that **sub-sample large ensembles of climate simulations** according to criteria that **align the phasing** of internal variability
- To explore the **predictability** of mean climate and climate extremes **on multiple time scales**.

Seamless S2D predictions (BSC) : Shadowing

- Decadal predictions and climate projections are constrained based on updated seasonal forecasts and recent observations.
- Constraining method to (1) increase the forecast quality by transferring short-term predictability into longer time scales, and (2) improve forecast consistency by avoiding “jumps” when switching from one horizon to other.
- The constrained seasonal to decadal (S2D) ensemble is also compared with the initialised multi-annual predictions produced in WP1.

Delgado-Torres et al. (2025; accepted

<https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-2025-3674>)

(a) Observation-based constraint: member selection in May

(c) Seasonal prediction-based constraint: member selection in May

Skill for Niño3.4

Seamless S2D predictions (BSC): Super User Applications

- The method is being tested for the case study on the humanitarian sector with Save The Children International (SCI) as Super User.
- SCI uses ENSO forecasts to anticipate precipitation conditions (<https://resourcecentre.savethechildren.net/document/predicting-the-impact-of-el-nino-on-families-and-children-a-household-economy-analysis-hea-assessment-in-malawi/>). The information is used to implement Anticipatory Action measures against malnutrition during the upcoming rainy season and consumption year in African countries (e.g. Malawi and Niger).
- Delgado-Torres et al. (2025; accepted <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-2025-3674>)

Seamless S2M Predictions (UOXF): Temporal Merging Pooling Ensemble Approach

- A new temporal merging method has been proposed to provide seamless climate information across lead times from 1 to 22 months, spanning seasonal to multi-annual (S2M) timescales
- Pooling Ensemble (Equation 1): “i” represents each forecast start date, “K” total start dates, W is the weighting function, and F represents forecast
- An ensemble-democracy approach is used to pool all ensemble members across all available lead times (i.e., from lead month 1 to lead month 22) of the target season (Abid et al. 2025) Preprint:

<https://www.researchsquare.com/article/rs-7725005/v1>

Temporal Merging

Each Start Date Forecast

$$Pooling\ Ensemble = \sum_{i=1}^K W_i F_i(m, x, y)$$

(Equation 1)

Merged Forecast

Source: Abid et al. 2025

Seamless S2M Predictions (UOXF): Value of the Forecast

- *Relative Economic Value (REV)* is a measure to estimate the value of the forecast
- It estimates economic value benefit, which can be achieved from the forecast
- Merged forecast is valuable than each start date forecast for most of the start dates to forecast at least 1 frost event, except for Nov

	Event observed (YES)	Event observed (NO)
Event Forecast (YES)	cost	cost
Event Forecast (NO)	loss	no

- *is climatological prob.*
- *is perfect forecast prob.*
Action only when event happens

Source: Abid et al. *in progress.*

Seamless S2M Predictions (UOXF): Super User Applications

- Temporal merging method is co-developed in the context of spring frost risk user need of Catalonian wine farmers (Abid et al. 2025)
- The application of the method is further explored to co-create heat wave risk information for British Red Cross resource planning managers (Balan Sarojini et al. in prep)
- Contribution of seamless climate prediction information to Agriculture, Emergency Response and Governance case studies in the monthly to multi-year timescales

Monthly Exceedance maps, ERA5

Summer heat wave skill, SEAS5, May starts

Source: Balan Sarojini, Abid & Weisheimer *in progress.*

Temporal merging of initialised and long-term projections (UKMO)

- Method constrains the variability in the projections by the residual predictable forecast signal once long-term forcing removed
- The constrained product adds skill at short timescales, but is tightly clustered due to a bias in the CMIP6 projections (see yellow and grey lines)
- Comparing the merged product (blue line and plume) with the original CMIP6 data (grey line and plume), reanalysis (black line) and the initialised decadal hindcasts (red line and plume) shows that merged product shows improved information after year 2000. Added value due to a simple trend weighting applied to the CMIP6 data beforehand is the difference between the grey and yellow lines and the effect on the merged product without the trend weighting is shown as light blue line

Constraining by T+1-9, T+2-9, ..., T+9 (smoothed weights by max)

Summer subpolar North Atlantic skill

Skill and reliability metrics to cover two types of decision making (UKMO)

- Merged product has skill at short lead times similar to decadal forecasts
- Merged product tends to be under-dispersive, i.e., the spread of the merged forecast ensemble is smaller than the variability in the observations. This is only partly due to the method which downweights realisations with unrealistically high variability
- Simplified trend weighting and errors in signal also matter

Summary (UKMO)

- Merge forecasts and projections based on the added value of the initialisation
- This works well in terms of skill at short lead times
- But the merged product is under-dispersive. This is mainly due to biases in the variability in some projections, overall bias in the projections, and will also depend on the weighting that has already been applied to the projections
- Lessons learnt – similar to Murphy et al (2025), there is a need for correction of variability before merging. Similar to Smith et al (2025), in some cases there is a need to bias correct the signal. But these corrections need R&D, and we are constrained to use the mainstream products that are available to users
- Still work in progress - Need to move from just the large-scale driver to the story about the impactful hazard

Temporal Merging

Achievements

- Development of a **seamless climate prediction system prototype**
 - to predict a regional extreme **spring frost frequency** for **Catalonian wine industry**, from **seasonal to multi-annual timescales** using a novel temporal merging technique – a **pooling ensemble approach (Abid et al. 2025)**.
- **Publication of constraining methods** (Delgado-Torres et al. 2025 (in the seasonal to multi-decadal timescales using predictions and projections); Cos et al 2024: Donat et al 2024 for large CMIP6 multi-model ensembles (>200 members), and apply the constraints to **improve near-term projections** of climate extremes (De Luca et al 2023)

Temporal Merging

Challenges

- **Artefacts** in the merged time series can occur when constraining different time scales, **due to specific model characteristics** (e.g. representation of trends or variations)
- **Limited sample size**; for calibration and skill estimation
- Limited skill in the raw forecasts
- Success in merging of the driver variable is yet to be mirrored in the merging of the hazard variable

ASPECT

"stitching"

"shadowing"

"merging"

Temporal Merging

Next Steps

- Source of predictability of spring minimum temperature in the seasonal to multi-annual time scale to add confidence to the merged product for Catalanian spring frost case study (in progress)
- To explore the usefulness of the forecasts and feasibility of extending the product to multi-decadal time scales (shadowing)
- To develop a temporally merged product for the co-designed indices for the Emergency Response sector's British Red Cross heat wave case study
- To explore possible upscaling of maximum and minimum temperature products of other European regions (e.g. Emilia Romagna for the Governance sector case study) (in progress).
- To explore constraining of the hazard variable based on the constrained driver variable (Pensions and Humanitarian sectors case studies).

"stitching"

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